

Dr. Marianne Kaufmann
for LCG RESEARCH GREECE

Dr. Carolina Diamandis Lab

Systemic use of Procaine: Synthesis, Pharmacokinetics, and Therapeutic Potential

Procaine, a chronically underestimated amino-ester compound, was synthesized over a century ago by Alfred Einhorn, with its hydrochloride form being marketed under the name 'Novocaine.' It followed the earlier use of cocaine as a local anesthetic in eye surgery by Carl Koller, after Sigmund Freud first identified cocaine's properties. Koller presented its anesthetic potential to the scientific community in 1884, reducing involuntary eye reflexes and enhancing surgical outcomes. Cocaine was later used in dentistry, but was eventually replaced by other anesthetics, such as lidocaine, in the 20th century. Procaine, now also known in a short form as 'PCN' remained in use until the 1960s but was then largely replaced by newer, less toxic local anesthetics with longer action. ^{References 1 to 19}

Medical use

Dr. Ana Aslan of Romania, starting in 1949, demonstrated procaine's efficacy in treating age-related dystrophic disorders

Contact: LCG Research, Dr. Marianne Kaufmann
research@lazar-consortium.com

and rheumatological conditions, using a composite of PCN and hematoporphyrin.

Synthesis and metabolism

Procaine can be synthesized through two methods: one involving the reaction of 4-aminobenzoic acid ethyl ester with 2-diethylaminoethanol and sodium ethanolate, and the other involving the oxidation of 4-nitrotoluene to 4-nitrobenzoic acid, followed by reaction with thionyl chloride and esterification with 2-diethylaminoethanol. At this point the nitro group is reduced. Procaine is hydrolytically cleaved in tissue by plasma cholinesterase into para-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) and diethylaminoethanol (DEAE). In patients with a normally working liver approximately 30% of Procaine is metabolized by the liver, with only 2% excreted unchanged through the kidneys.^{1,2,5,17,19}

Neurological and cardiovascular effects

Procaine blocks acetylcholine synthesis in all parts of the parasympathetic nervous system and preganglionic neurons of the sympathetic system. It normalizes neurotransmitter balance in the brain, affects brain regions associated with sensory-emotional transformation, and exhibits beta-blocker-like effects, stabilizing stress-induced physiological responses. It reduces catecholamine levels, weakens sympathetic system activity, and has antiarrhythmic and oxygen-conserving effects on the heart. As a coronary dilator, is believed able to strengthen vascular integrity.^{1,12,16}

Mitochondrial Effects

Procaine enhances cellular respiration, particularly through its high redox potential, and protects cells by stimulating cellular regeneration. It has been shown to significantly increase the efficacy of various pharmaceuticals, including antirheumatic, antihypertensive, antidiabetic, antidepressant, and antiviral agents on the mitochondrial level. Procaine is often used in combination therapies, enhancing the effectiveness of various medications, even at significantly lower doses.^{14,15,17,18,19}

Other effects

In diabetes management, PCN has been shown to improve glycemic control and reduce complications. It also enhances the effects of oral anti-diabetics and insulin, improving insulin sensitivity. Additionally, procaine works synergistically with antihistamines in treating allergies and asthma, reducing inflammation and spasms, and aiding as a booster in asthma management.^{1,6,7,9,10}

Cerebral neurotransmission

Procaine can correct imbalances directly in cerebral neurotransmission, especially when combined with benzodiazepines or neuroleptics, potentially reducing the dosage of these medications without posing an addiction risk. This makes it a very promising candidate for future new psychotropic drugs.^{7,8,19}

Dosage

Clinical cases suggest dosages ranging from 20mg to 60mg per intramuscular injection (maximum 200mg), with a daily limit of 500mg advised in the literature.¹⁹

Conclusion

There is significant potential in procaine's pharmacological applications. While its full utility is yet to be harnessed by the pharmaceutical industry, physicians may consider its off-label use responsibly.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

External funding

None.

Disclaimer

The information (and all observations) provided in this paper are for educational and informational purposes only and is not intended as a substitute for professional medical advice, diagnosis, or treatment. The therapies and applications of Procaine described herein are based on historical and current medical research and practice. However, they should **not** be construed as accepted or standard treatments. Readers are strongly advised to consult with qualified healthcare professionals before considering any of the therapies or applications mentioned in this document. The author and publisher of this document disclaim any liability for any direct, indirect, consequential, or other damages arising directly or indirectly from any use of the information contained herein. This document does not endorse or recommend any specific tests, physicians, products, procedures, opinions, or other information that may be mentioned. Reliance on any information provided in this document is solely at your own risk.

References

1. Klein, Wolfgang., Kocsis, Franz. Einfluss von Procain auf den DNA-Metabolismus: Vortrag, 3. Wiener Symposium über experimentelle Gerontologie, 9. und 10. Mai 1980
2. Pohl, Michael. Blockade sympatischer und vagaler Herzefferenzen durch pericardiale Lokalanästhesie mit Procain an Katzen. n.p. 1980
3. Bloß, Helmut. Vergleichende Untersuchungen über die Herzgiftwirkung von Chlorprocain und Procain, n.p., 1956
4. Diethelm, Andreas. Wachstumshemmung von Mammakarzinomzellen durch Procain. Bern, 1989
5. Kühnhardt, Dagmar. Einfluß von Procain auf die zelluläre Immunantwort, n.p., 2005
6. Mayer, Winfried. Molekülkomplexe und Radikalbildung mit Procain, n.p., 1981
7. Ockermann, Rainer. Die Wirkung von Procain und Xylocain auf zentralnervöses Gewebe:

- Dosis-Wirkungsbeziehung und qualitative Effekte nach Untersuchungen an isolierten Froschnetzhäuten. Frankfurt am Main, 1973
8. Miesterreck, Helmut. Experimentelle Grundlagen für die intravenöse Anwendung von Procain und Diäthylaminoäthanol. Berlin (West) 1953
 9. Schlickeisen, G. (1958). Über intracisternale Injektionen von Procain und Procain-Coffein-Gemisch beim Kaninchen. Freie Universität Berlin
 10. Meisel, Gisela. Gewebesclearance von 131 J unter Einwirkung von Procain, Coffein und L-Ascorbinsäure und den Komplexen Procain und Coffein (Impletol oder Jecoffin) und Procain und L-Ascorbinsäure. 1967.
 11. Mohs, Martin. Synthese und Eigenschaften neuer isosterer Derivate des Procain. Original: University of California, 1962
 12. Mark VH, Sweet WH, Ervin FR. Role of Brain Disease in Riots and Urban Violence. JAMA. 1968;203(5):368–369. doi:10.1001/jama.1968.03140050052020
 13. SLEMONS JM, JOHNSON JM. CESAREAN SECTION UNDER PROCAIN ANESTHESIA. JAMA. 1920;74(13):882–884. doi:10.1001/jama.1920.02620130018008
 14. Ostfeld A, Smith CM, Stotsky BA. The systemic use of procaine in the treatment of the elderly: a review. J Am Geriatr Soc. 1977 Jan;25(1):1-19. doi: 10.1111/j.1532-5415.1977.tb00917.x. PMID: 12204.p
 15. Moore DC. Local anesthetic drugs: tissue and systemic toxicity. Acta Anaesthesiol Belg. 1981 Dec;32(4):283-300. PMID: 7034447.
 16. Zhu J. [Recent progress in diagnosis and treatment of the injury to the peripheral nerve]. Zhongguo Xiu Fu Chong Jian Wai Ke Za Zhi. 2006 Apr;20(4):319-23. Chinese. PMID: 16683422.
 17. Patent: WO2006021166A1
 18. JOSE E. USUBIAGA, FRANK MOYA, JAIME A. WIKINSKI, REGINA WIKINSKI, LILIA E. USUBIAGA, RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PASSAGE OF LOCAL ANAESTHETICS ACROSS THE BLOOD-BRAIN BARRIER AND THEIR EFFECTS ON THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM, British Journal of Anaesthesia, Volume 39, Issue 12, 1967, Pages 943-947, ISSN 0007-0912. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/39.12.943>
 19. Unpublished data